

*EEVC: European Battery, Hybrid and Fuel Cell Electric Vehicle
Congress
Geneva, Switzerland, 13-15 March 2018*

**Grid services for electromobility: NeMo's approach towards
ensuring EV charging QoS and power system robustness through
ICT applications**

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Abstract

Smart charging aims at shaping EV fleet demand in a manner that is power grid friendly without compromising charging parameters at an extent that would be non desirable from the EV driver [1]. Charging flexibility, i.e non strict timeframes for charging operations stems from prolonged vehicle parking time between commutes, during work hours or late night hours [2]. Moreover, decreasing EV charge duration known as "fast charging", further increases the amount of time during which charging operations can be shifted from one timeslot to another, thus further enhancing possibilities for intelligent management of charging operations. Many other aspects of such intelligent control can further increase efficiency; integration of real time energy pricing or of renewable energy sources could lead to both lower energy cost and environmental impact [3]. Building smart charging applications requires collaboration between numerous entities, since many aspects related to energy and charging operations management have to be addressed.

From the energy management perspective, actors such as energy retailers should connect to charging provider operators in order to ensure power flows [4]. Power system stability at the EV charging management level must also be monitored and corrective processes should also be included in the lifecycle of smart charging. Therefore, DSO integration is also essential.

On the EV side, ease of charging operations entails, finding compatible charging spots, calculating required charging energy and booking charging sessions. Electromobility providers (EMP) manage the latter on behalf of the EV driver [5].

Integration of all smart charging related actors, in most cases follows the classic patterns of ICT application development where application programmer interfaces are implemented by different actors in order to make systems interoperable. However, in an ever increasing ecosystem of charging infrastructure including the introduction of more actors providing services can be beneficial for all charging operations as long as they can be discoverable by associated business actors and EV drivers. Such functionality can be integrated in service oriented based applications in terms of dynamical invocation of previously unknown services. A set of tools and a common information model, standardizing service invocations would still be a requirement for such an architecture to be implemented. NeMo [6], a 4 year 2020 horizon project will define the architectural components and will implement a service oriented architecture that will among other applications, build EV smart charging.

The following diagram depicts a UML sequence diagram of the smart charging approach, consisting of two diagrams. In the first diagram a indicative sequence diagram showing the charging negotiation and booking process is depicted. The second diagram focuses on energy procurement and grid capacity setpoint negotiation in order to ensure grid quality.

During the charging negotiation phase the electromobility provider (EMP) initially receives a charging request from the driver. Subsequently it polls the EV in order to calculate the energy requirement of the vehicle. Once received, the energy requirements along with other information such as charging socket type specifications and EV parking time are transmitted by the EMP to the charging provider operator (CPO). The CPO can calculate the charging proposition taking into account charging flexibility and given overall capacity constraints of the charging infrastructure and make a charging proposition to the EMP which visualizes and presents it to the end user for authorization of a selected option. The EMP further informs the CPO the selected charging profile and proceeds with the booking.

During the energy procurement and capacity setpoint definition phase, a CPO can search a service finder component which dynamically searches for available energy retail resources. The finder returns provides a list of services of which one is selected. The CPO can proceed with the energy planning phase and check that capacity constraints do not comprise grid power quality.

Figure 1 Load management sequence diagrams for smart charging reservation and negotiation of EV infrastructure capacity limits.

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